

Performance analysis of MBR for zero liquid discharge in educational-cum-residential campus

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ABSTRACT

Recycling and reuse of treated wastewater is a prime tool for achieving Zero Liquid Discharge. The work analyzes the feasibility and performance of a Membrane Bio-Reactor (MBR) technology for treating wastewater produced from an educational-cum-residential campus in Maharashtra. ZeeWeed-500d Ultrafiltration membrane followed by UV disinfection is used to treat the wastewater and reuse it for gardening and cleaning purpose in the campus. The treatment sequence resulted in reduction of BOD₅ of 220 mg/l to less than 10 mg/l, COD from 550 mg/l to less than 50 mg/l and TSS from 50 mg/l to less than 5 mg/l. The membrane fouling is prevented by Clean-In-Place system consisting of aeration system for scouring and sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and citric acid to target organic and inorganic foulants respectively. Sludge obtained is utilized as manure after passing in filter press. No waste or liquid waste is generated in the process. The process is controlled by programmable logic controller (PLC) avoiding any manual involvement.

Keywords: Wastewater Treatment, MBR, ZLD, BOD, PLC.

INTRODUCTION

The demand of fresh water is increasing day by day with increase in population and living standard. This leads to rise in generation of wastewater due to which stress on wastewater treatment facilities is shooting up. One of the solution for this problem is decentralisation of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs)¹. Again there are numerous methods available to treat this wastewater but their efficiency in terms of effluent quality is not satisfactory. In the course of previous decades, membrane based treatment methods like Membrane Bio-Reactor (MBR) have become popular at industrial level as well as for municipal wastewater^{2, 3, 4, 5}. MBR produces effluent of superior quality than conventional activated sludge (CAS)¹, rotating biological reactor (RBC)⁶ etc. and requires lesser area because of omission of sedimentation unit⁷. But MBRs are costly and require energy for their working⁸ which in turn increases emission of greenhouse gases (GHGs)⁹. Another problem associated with MBR is membrane

fouling¹⁰⁻¹¹. Membrane fouling depends on various parameters like pre-treatment efficiency⁹, velocity field of fluid¹², degree of membrane cleaning and maintenance¹³, HRT¹⁴ etc. Hybrid membranes have been developed to tackle limitations of conventional membrane bio-reactor (CMBR). These include combining RBC with MBR⁶, CAS followed by MBR¹⁵, dynamic MBR¹⁶ and MBR with sorption or advanced oxidation⁹. This paper evaluates performance of an MBR based WWTP on the basis of effluent quality and cleaning and maintenance to facilitate zero liquid discharge in the campus.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study is performed in an educational-cum-residential campus located in Shirpur, Maharashtra. The water source for matching water demands and for discharging wastewater is Tapi River flowing close to campus. The river serves a total water demand of 900 KLD for the campus. The campus have Water treatment plant based on sedimentation-filtration-RO technology. Due to environmental concern and reducing freshwater demand, a sewage treatment plant (STP) of capacity 900 KLD based on Membrane Bio-Reactor (MBR) technology has been setup in the campus. The flow scheme of the STP is depicted in the **Figure**.

1. STP receives water from two sewers, one from educational building and other from residential buildings. Wastewater is generated from bathrooms and water closets, mess and kitchen, laundry and laboratories. Pre-treatment in the form of coarse and fine screen, oil skimmer, grit separator and anoxic tank are provided before feeding wastewater to bio-reactor. MBR system consists of aeration tank followed by Ultra Filtration membrane. The plant is equipped with Clean In-place system prevent membrane fouling and a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) unit to prevent any mechanical interventions except in some cases. The PLC continuously runs a PID (proportional-integral-derivative) loop for Trans Membrane Pressure (TMP) while in production. The effluent generated by the STP can be used to serve secondary purposes of gardening, cleaning and flushing.

Filtration and permeation

Filtration, or permeation, consists of drawing clean water from the mixed liquor through the membrane fibers via the permeate pump. Water is produced from each cycle during the filtration period for a duration of 11 minutes, followed by a 30 second relaxation. Dedicated permeate/process pump is provided per cycle for filtration/backpulse purposes with a common standby for multiple cycles. The vacuum generated by the permeate pump draws permeate from the outside-in through the membranes and discharges it to the Permeate Storage Tank. The

variable speed pumps are controlled by PLC to maintain the permeate-flow demand. The PLC uses the lower of the control outputs from the flow loop and TMP loop.

FIGURE. 1. Flow scheme of Sewage Treatment Plant

Membrane fouling

As the feed is drawn through the membranes during filtration, solids are removed which accumulate on the membrane surface. As the solids accumulate, they restrict the flow through the membranes and eventually membrane cleaning is required to maintain the filtered water flow rate. Moreover, the membranes can experience fouling caused by accumulation of organic matter or crystallized salts within the membrane fiber pores.

In the former case, the membranes are immersed in mixed liquor in the membrane tanks (**Figure 2**). The membranes are aerated using state-of-the-art aeration design that is integral to the membrane cassette. The membrane cassette is aerated to provide a mechanical cleaning action. Coarse bubbles generated by aeration grid is used to scour the outside surface of the membrane and move mixed liquor solids away from the membrane fibers. The air is provided

by a common aeration blower and is delivered at the bottom of each membrane cassette using a single airline. The air exits the aerators located at the bottom of each cassette and scour the membrane surface thus removing the solids accumulated on it ensuring a sustainable operation of the system. Whenever a membrane cycle is in production, membrane scour aeration is required to maintain consistent permeability of the membrane. The aeration also minimizes the effect of concentration polarization which is recognized as a significant membrane fouling mechanism.

FIGURE.2: Mechanical cleaning of membrane cassette by air scouring

In the later case, cleaning of the membranes in this circumstance to restore the permeability requires use of a Clean-In-Place system. This involves an extended backpulse combined with low concentration of chemical addition using sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and citric acid to target organic and inorganic foulants respectively (**Table 1**). Such cleans are intended to maintain membrane permeability and extend the time between recovery cleans.

TABLE 1. Maintenance Cleaning Summary and Schedule

Parameters (All trains in operation)	NaOCl	Citric Acid	Units
Frequency	2-3 Times	1-2 Times	Per week
Total Downtime per train	50-60	50-60	min
Dosing Concentration of chemical in ppm	200	2000	Ppm or mg/L
Specific Gravity of chemical	1.168	1.22	-
Concentration (% by weight)	10.3	50	%
Dosing Pump flow rate	45LPH	86LPH	-

Recovery cleaning is required to restore the permeability of the membrane once the membrane becomes fouled. The recovery cleaning procedure consists of a chemical backpulse sequence, followed by a chemical soak period (**Table 2**). Backpulsing involves reversing the flow through the membranes to dislodge any particles that may have adhered to the membrane surface. The backpulse tank is automatically filled with permeate which is used for the backpulse process. If required, hypochlorite may be added to the backpulse tank to maintain a concentration of < 5.0 mg/L to prevent bacterial growth.

TABLE 2. Recovery Cleaning Summary and Schedule

Parameters (All trains in operation)	NaOCl	Citric Acid	Units
Frequency	4	4	Per year
Total Downtime per train	7.5	7.5	Hours
Dosing Concentration of chemical Note2	1,100	2,200	mg/L
Concentration (% by weight)	10.3	50	%
Chemical flow per R-Clean	513LPH	200LPH	-

Details of necessary parameters for the STP are presented in **Table 3**.

TABLE 3. Parameters for MBR system

Parameters	Unit	Min	Optimum	Max
MLSS	mg/l	6000	8000	10000
Bioreactor pH	-	6.8	7	7.5
Bioreactor DO	ppm	1.5	2	3
Permeate Turbidity	NTU	-	< 1	< 5
Permeate pH	-	6.5	7	7.5
Production flow	m ³ /hr.	20	35	37.5
Backpulse flow	m ³ /hr.	-	-	45
Production time	minute	7	9	10
Backpulse Time	sec	40	50	60
TMP during Production	kg/cm ²	0	-	-0.4
TMP during Backpulse	kg/cm ²	0	-	0.4

Note – Production Flow is as per demand of the plant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wastewater characteristics at the inlet and outlet of the STP are tabulated in **Table 4**.

TABLE 4. Wastewater characteristics of MBR based STP

S. No.	Parameters	Unit	Result		MPCB Limits	CPCB Limits
			Inlet	Outlet		
1	pH	-	7.5	7.7	5.5-9.0	5.5-9.0
2	Total Suspended Solids	mg/l	15.0	1	100.0	100.0
3	Total Dissolved solids	mg/l	500	150	2100.0	NS
4	Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)	mg/l	540.0	35.0	250.0	250
5	Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)	mg/l	220.0	9.5	100.0	30
6	Chlorides	mg/l	145.5	50.5	600.0	NS
7	Sulphates	mg/l	50.4	40.0	1000.0	NS
8	Oil & Grease	mg/l	15	NIL	10.0	10.0
9	Total Coliform (MPN)	per 100ml	NA	9.0	NS	NS
10	E.coli	per 100ml	NA	7.0	NS	NS

NS: Not Specified

NA: Not Analyzed

The MBR system has removed 210 mg/l of BOD, 505 mg/l COD, 14 mg/l of TSS and 350 mg/l of TDS.

CONCLUSION

Decreasing availability of freshwater and increasing stress on water bodies to fulfil the demand require approaches for recycling and reusing wastewater. The MBR based STP set up is an example of such an approach. The efficiency of the plant for BOD is 95%, COD is 93%, TSS is 93% and TDS is 70%. The discharged effluent is of high quality which can be used to meet demands of water for gardening and cleaning in the campus. MBR system suffice present requirement of managing and utilizing wastewater generated. The membrane fouling is well controlled by available methods of aeration, Clean-In Place system and recovery cleaning. Excess effluent can be stored and supplied to nearby agricultural areas in dry seasons. Since, effluent quality is close to IS-10500:2012, it can be used for in the laundry also. With some extra treatment methods to reduce coliform and COD, the excess water can be discharged to

open ground for recharging groundwater. The construction works going on in the campus and nearby areas requires water whose demand can be fulfilled by the effluent. Overall, total effluent produced can be used to fulfil various demands resulting in zero discharge to nearby water body.

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